

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP2 - Pilot implementation and Open Call “Writing Across Borders” outputs

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“Writing Across Borders” outputs

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Project Overview

COESO (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues) is a 3-year participatory research project, funded by the European Commission through a *Science with and for Society* grant. At the heart of the project are ten citizen science pilots, representing a variety of social sciences and arts disciplines, societal challenges and types of engagement with citizens in different European countries.

Pilot 5, coordinated by GHI | PRO (MWS), brought together a historical and comparative perspective on migration, with two distinct initiatives:

- The first initiative, “Writing Across Borders: Narratives of Migration, 1800–1950” builds citizen scientist skills and creates a network of researchers able to work with historical documents and participate in machine-learning activities. This first initiative feeds into:
- the second one, the “Network Migrant Knowledge”. In this second initiative, the central object of research are migrants as carriers and producers of knowledge.

Historical Perspective: Writing Across Borders: Narratives of Migration, 1800–1950

“Writing Across Borders” organized community sourced transcriptions of letters and diaries. It provides a Web-based interface to facilitate such activities as well as for the presentations of the documents and resulting transcriptions.

The first significant step was the launch of <https://www.migrantconnections.org/> in March 2022. This new bi-lingual (English / German) platform integrates the transcription environment for citizen scientists working on letters sent from the German-speaking lands to immigrants in the United States (formerly “German Heritage in Letters”) with the new workspace for the Writing Across Borders initiative.

Community sourced transcriptions are supported through the integration of the open-source tool [Scripto](https://scripto.org/) (<https://scripto.org/>). After registration with their email address, citizen scientists can directly start transcribing the available sources directly in their browser:

Once the transcription has been finalized and checked as part of the quality assurance process, it is publicly made available. So far, almost 300 letters with transcriptions and/or translations have been published and enriched with metadata that provide more information on the letters and their authors (https://www.migrantconnections.org/s/mobile_en/item?Search=&property%5B0%5D%5Bproperty%5D=170&property%5B0%5D%5Btype%5D=req&property%5B0%5D%5Btext%5D=transcribed) .

A recording of the launch event that brought together experts on historical migration with an active citizen transcriber to learn more about their collaboration can be watched online at <https://www.ghi-dc.org/news-show/launch-of-new-digital-research-infrastructure-migrant-connections>.

In addition to the Scripto-based environment for manual transcriptions, we developed an online training module for (Semi-)automated Handwritten Text Recognition for diaries and other ego-documents through Transkribus, the machine-learning platform originally developed within the EU-funded READ project (<https://transkribus.eu/>).

Using machine-learning models for automated transcription of a diary

The tutorial has been published through the Pilots' Blog (<https://migconn.hypotheses.org/140>). It received initial testing and feedback based on a variety of sources provided by the participants of the final symposium (see below).

Comparative Perspective: Migrant Knowledge Network

With regards to the second initiative, the “Migrant Knowledge Network” continued to publish original contributions aiming at a wide international audience both within and outside of academia on its dedicated website <https://migrantknowledge.org/blog/>. During the past two years, 31 original contributions from members of the network have been published complemented by various news posts such as conference calls and new book announcements.

Particularly noteworthy is the mini-series “What Did They Know?” (<https://migrantknowledge.org/2022/10/28/intro-baden-migrants-miniseries/>) developed within a University course featuring a contribution by Hannah Laubrock based on a series of migrant letters from the second half of the 19th century (<https://migrantknowledge.org/2022/11/29/emigrant-correspondence/>).

Final Symposium

*R.M.S. "Queen Mary"
13th July 1938
23156A*

*Wenn ich mich jetzt, 3 Stunden
nach der Abfahrt, zum Sch
hinsetze, so tue ich das,
mir von allen Feinden
bis jetzt hatte, nichts?
Zu sehr hat mi
von meinen lieben
Um 6 Uhr au
Amerika
der He
be
die*

Document /in/g Transit

**Final Symposium of "Writing Across Borders"
(COESO Pilot 5)**

Bonn, Bad Godesberg, November 21-22, 2022

ghi Washington

"How, with whom, and for whom do we read our sources?" was the central question of the final symposium in Bonn, Bad Godesberg, November 21-22, 2022. It united transcribers, machine-learning "trainers" and scholars working with (mostly handwritten) ego-documents (letters and diaries) written in time of transit. Collaboration with citizens as well as introducing new technologies both point towards new innovative ways of doing traditional source-centered research with the potential to relate historical with contemporary perspectives on migration.

Drawing on the current research of the participants with a strong focus on forced migration in the 1930s/40s, on the one hand, external aspects of the documents such as materiality, scripts, languages and genre were discussed. On the other hand, shifts, breaks, as well as continuities in themes, tone, and style across time and place are highly significant for the source interpretation. A hands-on session acquainted with the technical means of automatically transcribing handwritten documents. In addition, the costs and gains of "deep" digitization were addressed.

Of particular value was the exchange with "Gruß und Kuss," a federally funded citizen science project focusing on love letters (<https://liebesebriefarchiv.de/projekt-gruss-kuss/>). They share many challenges

concerning recruitment and sustainable participation of citizen scientists into the collaborative research on ego-documents.

Additional Activities

A dedicated blog <https://migconn.hypotheses.org/> has been set-up on hypotheses.org for public outreach. In addition to reports on the significant steps in the project, we managed to publish a first research article from a citizen scientist, Eberhard Pelke, who studies the work of German-American bridge engineers.¹ We intend to continue to publish additional findings on historic and contemporary transatlantic migration by non-academic researchers on this blog.

In addition to the activities within “Writing Across Borders”, members of Pilot 5 took an active role in the co-design activities for VERA by providing WP3 with input and feedback based on the needs and experiences from their project.

Conclusion

Within COESO project’s Pilot 5, citizen scholars have been collecting sources, transcribing and translating them, as well as creating metadata and writing stories about what they had found out. By listening to these stories, we realized that what academics find essential and important to write about does not necessarily correspond to what lay people expect to hear. Connecting research and society is therefore a mutual learning experience for both sides. Scholars will benefit tremendously by broadening their usual circles and changing perspectives to see who they are doing research for and with whom. Since volunteers are driven by different incentives compared to professional historians, a participatory research project needs to rethink its various tasks, in order to make them interesting and manageable for a wider range of people.

“Migrant Connections” aims to remain a sustainable platform for the cooperative research started within Pilot 5 of COESO. We will continue to enhance the collection and train both citizen scholars and academics on how to use web publishing platforms and automated handwritten text recognition platforms for transcribing handwritten documents. In addition, we plan to connect our documents with a wide range of administrative sources such as passenger lists or census documents as well as genealogical databases, an area where citizen scientists have been building up a wealth of information with great potential for the future study of transatlantic migration.

¹ Pelke, E. Brücken über den Atlantik: Zwei Generationen von Ingenieuren, in: Migrant Connections, October 10, 2022, <https://migconn.hypotheses.org/55>